

STRATEGIES FOR REDUCING SIDE EFFECTS OF DRUGS IN ONCOGEMATOLOGICAL DISEASES

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Relevance: oncogematological diseases, especially in children, can cause serious negative effects and long-term health problems. The side effects of the drugs used to treat these conditions can reduce the quality of life of patients, making the treatment process more difficult. Treatments such as chemotherapy, immunotherapy, radiotherapy can cause significant damage to children's immune system and overall health. Therefore, in oncogematological diseases, it is of urgent importance to reduce the side effects of drugs, increase the effectiveness of treatment and improve the quality of life of patients. Today, effective treatments are needed to reduce the number of patients dying from children's oncogematological diseases, but it is always relevant to reduce side effects and create safer and more effective therapy for patients. This research will help develop strategies aimed at minimizing the negative effects of drugs.

Purpose of the study: the study envisages the following main objectives: to develop strategies for choosing rational drugs to reduce the side effects of basic treatments such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Taking into account genetic and clinical characteristics when prescribing drugs through an individual approach to children. To study the effectiveness of drug combinations to reduce side effects of drugs. To develop new treatment protocols and ensure effective and safe treatment through clinical use.

Methods and methods: literature analysis: an analysis of existing scientific literature, clinical research and practical experiments on reducing drug side effects in the treatment of Oncogematological diseases. Statistical analysis: mathematical and statistical methods are used to analyze research results and obtain statistically significant results.

Results: the expected results of the study include: Reducing side effects: with the help of the selection of rational drugs, their combination and genetic individual approaches, even fewer side effects are observed in the treatment of oncogematological diseases in children. Improving the effectiveness of treatment: by testing new combinations of drugs, as well as individually adjusting the dosage and treatment courses, the effectiveness of the treatment of oncogematological diseases increases. New protocols: new treatment protocols will be developed to reduce the side effects of medications, ensuring safer and more effective treatment for children. Pharmacogenetic analysis: with the help of pharmacogenetic analysis, results are obtained in the study of the individual effects of drugs, as well as in the optimization of genetically based therapies. Improved quality of life: as a result of reduced side effects and effective treatment, the overall quality of life in children is significantly improved..

Conclusions: developing effective strategies to reduce drug side effects in the treatment of Oncogematological diseases, provides safe and effective treatment options for patients. The approaches developed in this study increase treatment effectiveness by providing an individual approach to drug selection, especially for children, optimizing treatment protocols, and applying genetic analysis. The results of the study will help to create safer and more effective methods for

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dealing with oncogematological diseases. These lead to a reduction in the side effects of drugs, especially for children, and an improvement in the quality of life.